

A PATH MODEL OF BEHAVIORAL REGULATION IN EXERCISE AMONG STUDENTS IN SPECIAL PROGRAM FOR SPORTS IN REGION XI

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A Path Model of Behavioral Regulation in Exercise among Students in Special Program for Sports in Region XI

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Abstract

This research aimed to determine the causal relationship of interconnected variables particularly, sleep quality, social support, basic psychological needs satisfaction and behavioral regulation in exercise among students in the Special Program for Sports in Region XI utilizing quantitative research that employed descriptive-correlational design with path analysis in the treatment of data. Three hundred seventy junior high school students under a special program for sports were selected through purposive sampling technique. Moreover, a set of survey questionnaires were used as instruments to obtain information from the respondents. Mean and standard deviation, Pearson-r, and path analysis were used for the treatment of data. The findings revealed that the sleep quality of the students is moderate. Social support and basic psychological needs satisfactions were high. On the other hand, the behavioral regulation in exercise is moderate. Furthermore, the social support and basic psychological needs satisfaction were highly correlated with behavioral regulation in exercise. Finally, the best fit model, social support, has a direct influence on the behavioral regulation in exercise. Sleep quality has an indirect influence on basic psychological needs satisfaction. Also, the basic psychological needs satisfaction has indirect influence on social support. The best fitting model for the behavior regulation in exercise was best anchored on social support.

Keywords: *physical education, sleep quality, social support, basic psychological need satisfaction, behavior regulation in exercise*

Introduction

Behavioral regulation includes managing actions, emotions, and responses, shaped by different factors to attain specific objectives or results (Smith, 2020). Students find it hard to control their exercise behavior, which makes it difficult for them to maintain consistent levels of physical activity. Several studies have investigated the factors contributing to these difficulties and their implications for promoting exercise adherence among students (Johnson & Smith, 2020). There is poor control over students' physical activity, which results in poor behavioral regulation in exercise. Only 10.8% of students participate in sports, indicating a noteworthy level of moderate physical activity. Thus, there is a trend of physical inactivity among students and is due to poor behavior regulation in exercise which leads to poor understanding of the motivational determinants of exercise behavior (Hancock & Bergman, 2023).

In China, intervention must be taken immediately to address students' poor behavioral regulation in exercise. Furthermore, research indicates that almost 70% of students fail to meet the physical exercise health standards, and some of them merely engage in physical exercise during the sports standards test. Moreover, studies on students' physical well-being carried out in 2010, 2015, and 2020 have consistently shown that Chinese university students' general level of physical fitness has been steadily declining. These studies have also shown several health issues, including insufficient sleep, obesity, and the sad occurrences of unexpected fatalities during sporting events (Feng et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, the poor behavior regulation in exercise led Filipino students to achieve a low benchmark in their attendance to physical fitness activities which showed that 61 percent of students don't exercise regularly (Dumlao-Abadilla, 2017). The poor behavior regulation in exercise is due to the limited understanding of the concepts and foundational facts in physical education (Bernardo et al., 2023). Consequently, Mungcal et al. (2021) stated that other people engage in sedentary behaviors and lack physical activity due to several obstacles that hinder their desire to engage in physical activity despite of the favorable health benefits, some people prefer passive activities and lack physical activity.

In Davao Region, Dumlao-Abadilla (2017) stated that the one reason for the students' poor exercise behavior regulation was the COVID-19 pandemic's effects on fitness, health, and physical activity. Negative impacts resulted from students' behavior regulation performance decreasing from rigorous to moderate. Students struggle greatly to maintain proper behavioral regulation when engaging in a variety of physical education activities. Hernandez (2021) stated that poor behavior regulation led the students to engage in sedentary behaviors and lack physical activity due to several obstacles that hinder their desire to engage in physical activity.

Sleep quality has a beneficial impact on behavior regulation during exercise. The results imply that improved sleep quality influences exercise behavior regulation without causing significant negative consequences. Consequently, better behavior regulation during exercise was discovered to have moderate to strong beneficial impacts on overall sleep quality, demonstrating moderate to largely strong positive effects (Gupta et al, 2021).

Wilson et al. (2019) found that social support significantly influences behavioral regulation of exercise of college students' as it influences their commitment and motivation to engage in physical activity. Studies constantly show that students are more likely to

keep to regular physical activity when they feel more social support from friends, family, and peers. This assistance serves as a motivating element that enhances people's desire to go beyond challenges and obstacles, which improves their capacity to successfully control their exercise behavior. Furthermore, establishing opportunities for social connections and mutual goals linked to physical activity, group-based fitness activities, peer interaction, and a supportive environment on college campuses can all help students better regulate their behavior when it comes to exercise.

On the other hand, Reis et al. (2020) stated that when psychological needs were satisfied, exercise behavior regulation improved. However, psychological needs are connected to behavioral regulation in exercise. Both directly recognized control, the satisfaction of the desire for competence had a dominant effect on behavioral regulation in exercise. In addition, Ryan & Deci (2015) confirms that satisfying basic psychological is closely linked to effective behavioral regulation in exercise. People who feel competent, connected to others, and autonomous are more likely to exercise regularly and exhibit higher self-regulation.

There was inadequate behavioral regulation among Filipino students to engage in physical exercise. Determining how Filipino students manage their behavior and how it links to how well they sleep and how much support they receive from their peers could offer useful new knowledge, thus expanding the scientific setting to this country seems essential. The researcher has not come across any studies that use a path analysis model to study students regulate their exercise behavior using three exogenous variables. Moreover, studies have examined the experiences and challenges faced by college students, there remains a significant gap in research focusing specifically on learners enrolled in Special Program in Sports within the Department of Education. Despite UNESCO's policy initiatives aimed at promoting quality physical education programs worldwide, including the encouragement of learners' engagement in physical activity, these practices have not been widely adapted or implemented in the context of physical education in the Philippines. The researcher has considered the presumptions above and decided to conduct the study to determine which of factors is most likely to influence students' behavioral regulation in exercise. This research will add to the body of previously undiscovered information by concentrating on three exogenous factors and one endogenous variable.

The objective of this study is to understand the connections and predicted pathways that exist between the different factors that affect how student exercise. The study can provide significant information for developing more successful interventions that will encourage sustained physical activity and improve the overall health outcomes of the students. As a result, this study aims to create the most accurate model of behavioral regulation in exercise among students, specifically in the Special Program for Sports. The findings may be presented in public forums, publication in journals, and publication on local, national, and international platforms. Hence, it can be widely disseminated to the school principals, teacher-coaches, and the stakeholders of the school through LAC session, training enhancement programs, within district to division level sessions. Furthermore, a dissemination plan may be created to inform stakeholders both internal and external of the outcomes of the study in a seminar workshop initiated by the Department of Education – Region XI. Finally, they may also add to the existing pool of knowledge on sleep quality, social support, basic psychological needs satisfaction and behavioral regulation in exercise among students in special program for sports, which could be valuable to future researchers as part of their future research development.

Research Questions

The study determined the path analysis model of behavioral regulation in exercise regarding sleep quality, social support, and basic psychological needs satisfaction among students in the Special Program for Sports in Region XI.

1. What is the level of sleep quality among special program for sports student in terms of:
 - 1.1. daytime dysfunction;
 - 1.2. restoration after sleep;
 - 1.3. difficulty falling asleep;
 - 1.4. difficulty in getting up;
 - 1.5. satisfaction with sleep; and
 - 1.6. difficulty in maintaining sleep?
2. What is the level of social support among special program for sports student in terms of:
 - 2.1. companionship;
 - 2.2. emotional;
 - 2.3. informational;
 - 2.4. instrumental; and
 - 2.5. validation?
3. What is the level of basic psychological needs satisfaction in exercise among special program for sports student in terms of:
 - 3.1. autonomy;
 - 3.2. competence; and
 - 3.3. relatedness?
4. What is the level of behavioral regulation in exercise among special program for sports student in terms of:
 - 4.1. amotivation;

- 4.2. external regulation;
- 4.3. introjected regulation;
- 4.4. identified regulation;
- 4.5. integrated regulation; and
- 4.6. intrinsic regulation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 5.1. sleep quality and behavioral regulation in exercise;
 - 5.2. social support and behavioral regulation in exercise; and
 - 5.3. basic psychological need satisfaction in exercise and behavioral regulation in exercise?
6. What model best fits the behavioral regulation in exercise among students in special program for sports?

Methodology

Research Design

This quantitative study utilized a descriptive-correlational design with path analysis. Quantitative research involves systematic collection and examination of numerical data to understand phenomena and evaluate hypotheses. With this method, data is analyzed using statistical tools, and conclusions are based on actual evidence (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Moreover, a descriptive research design allows for the observation and description of occurrences without the need for manipulation or influence. It seeks to give an accurate depiction of traits, actions, or viewpoints within a group or sample. (Neuman, 2014). Correlation refers to the relationship between two or more variables, and it shows how changes in one variable are related to changes in another. The degree and direction of a relationship between variables are measured by correlation, which does not imply causality (Gravetter & Forzano, 2018). Path analysis is a research technique that looks at the direct and indirect impacts of several variables on an outcome variable to investigate complex interactions between variables. Evaluating the intensity and significance of routes connecting variables in a causal model enables researchers to test theoretical theories and hypotheses (Kline, 2015).

This design was used by the researcher because it evaluates theoretical frameworks and hypotheses by determining the magnitude and significance of connections among variables within a causal structure. The study aimed to investigate the levels of behavioral regulation in exercise, social support, basic psychological need satisfaction and sleep quality among special programs for sports students in Region XI. It also measured the relationship between behavior regulation in exercise and the following: sleep quality, social support, and basic psychological need satisfaction. Also, the path analysis was used to focus on determining the best fit model on behavioral regulation in exercise of the students.

Respondents

The 370 respondents of this study were the students from the special program for sports (SPS) and were chosen through a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling, a method used in qualitative research involves carefully choosing units or individuals according to predefined standards that correspond with the goals of the study. Purposive sampling entails a careful and purposeful selection procedure, in contrast to random sampling techniques, where each piece has an equal chance of selection (Nikolopoulou, 2022). To be included in the study, a student had to meet certain requirements: enrolled in a public high school under Special Program for Sports in Region XI, signing the Assent Forms and providing an Informed Consent, and being willing to participate in the research. Conversely, the exclusion criteria for research participants included being enrolled in a private school, not being covered by the SPS program, refusing to participate, failing to sign the assent form, and not having given informed consent. Meanwhile, students who opted to withdraw prematurely due to any cause without justification could withdraw from the study.

The study was conducted in Region XI, Philippines. It includes five southeast provinces of Mindanao: Davao Oriental, Davao Occidental, Davao del Norte, Davao del Sur, and Davao de Oro. The researcher chose the public secondary school since it offers special programs for sports. The researcher proposed that, special program for sport students had trouble controlling their behavior while exercising, which hindered their growth and eventually affected their health and academic performance. School A is in Davao de Oro located in San Mariano, Maragusan, Davao de Oro. School B is in Malita, Davao Occidental. School C lies within Mankilam, Tagum City. School D is in Baganga, Davao Oriental. School E is in Torres Street, Población District, Davao City.

Instruments

The researcher used adopted questionnaires. All parts will be validated by a panel of experts and undergo pilot testing. To measure the students' sleep quality based on the study of (Yi et al., 2006) entitled "Development of the Sleep Quality Scale." The questionnaire showed an overall alpha coefficient was 0.91, which is described as very high consistency. Meanwhile, to measure the social support for physical activity among SPS students is an adopted based on the study of Golaszewski and Bartholomew (2018) entitled "The Development of the Physical Activity and Social Support Scale." The overall Cronbach alpha was 0.87, which is interpreted as very high. The basic psychological need based on the study of (Vlachopoulos & Michailidou, 2009) entitled "Development and Initial Validation of a Measure of Autonomy, Competence, and Relatedness in Exercise: The Basic Psychological Needs in Exercise Scale." with a Cronbach alpha of 0.73. The behavioral regulation in exercise based on the study of Chai et al. (2022) entitled, "Psychometric

properties of the Malay version of the Behavioral Regulation in Exercise Questionnaire (BREQ-3)” with Cronbach’s alpha of 0.88 measured on a 5-point scale where 1 is regarded as very low, 2 as low, 3 as moderate, 4 as high and 5 as very high.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that ethical considerations were addressed by thoroughly examining the study's methodology. After all respondents had completed the survey, the data subsequently underwent analysis and computation. Primarily, adherence to research protocols, including essential ethical considerations, was imperative for conducting the survey.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion from the data gathered based on the responses of the respondents. The data shown in this chapter are the quantitative results which include the descriptive level of the variables, the significance of the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables, associations among the latent variables and the indicators through a measurement model, summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Path Analysis Model, the direct and indirect effects of the exogenous variables on Behavior Regulation in Exercise of the Best Fit Model, and estimates of Variable Regression Weights in Best Fit Model.

Level of Sleep Quality of Students in Special Program for Sports

Table 1 presents the results of the study on the level of sleep quality of students in special program for sports in terms of daytime dysfunction, restoration after sleep, difficulty falling asleep, difficulty in getting up, satisfaction with sleep and difficulty in maintaining sleep. The overall mean of sleep quality of students in special program for sports in region XI is 2.98 which describes as moderate. The overall standard deviation is 0.42 which is less than 1.00 which represents uniformity of responses from the participants and the responses are not so dispersed from each other. The moderate level implies that the sleep quality of students is sometimes manifested. A moderate sleep quality among students limits their improvement and athletic performance, underscoring the essential importance of high-quality sleep. The finding present above is aligned with the results of Newsom (2023) which cited that if an individual does not sleep enough, he or she may do less physical activity during the day and lose muscle strength. A lack of sleep may also compromise a person's ability to exercise safely, as sleep-deprived athletes are more likely to sustain injuries during sports.

Table 1. Level of Sleep Quality of Students in Special Program for Sports

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Daytime Dysfunction	3.02	0.87	Moderate
Restoration After Sleep	3.38	0.96	Moderate
Difficulty in Falling Asleep	3.22	0.83	Moderate
Difficulty in Getting Up	3.34	0.86	Moderate
Satisfaction with Sleep	3.33	0.94	Moderate
Difficulty Maintaining Sleep	3.24	1.01	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.98	0.42	Moderate

Note: Reversed mean scores for Daytime Dysfunction, Difficulty in Falling Asleep, Difficulty in Getting Up, and Difficulty in Maintaining Sleep is computed to get the overall mean.

The indicator with the highest mean is restoration after sleep. The means of this indicator restoration after sleep ranged from 3.06 to 3.73. The category mean is 3.38 described as moderate which means restoration after sleep is sometimes manifested. This implies that the student’s restoration after sleep is vital for managing mood and may be more prone to mood swings like irritability or anxiety, which can affect their motivation and enthusiasm for training and competition. Such findings concur with the conclusions of Brinkman et al. (2023), that if an individual awoke feeling refreshed and rested, they probably had a restorative night's sleep. Restorative sleep occurs when brain activity during sleep aids in mental and physical healing, effectively performing a reset in preparation for the following day's activities. Additionally, it further explains the avowal of Smith (2021) which pointed out that people need to get enough sleep to replenish the energy expend during the day if people want to be productive and maintain excellent health. Meanwhile the indicator with lowest mean is daytime dysfunction. The means of this indicator daytime dysfunction ranged from 2.77 to 3.26. The category mean is 3.02 described as moderate which means daytime dysfunction is sometimes manifested. This means that students experience decreased energy levels, reduced focus, and slower reaction times, which can compromise their ability to execute skills effectively and make quick decisions on the field or court. The findings are congruent with the study of Padel (2019) that excessive daytime sleepiness is associated with worse overall health outcomes, increased risk of work-related or traffic-related accidents, and decreased risk of engaging in physical exercise for individuals of similar age. Also, this aligns with the research carried out by Benz et al. (2020), which revealed that it is important to note that moderate daytime dysfunction can have a significant impact on an individual's ability to engage in regular physical activity. Students with moderate sleep are frequently more tired, which affects their capacity to concentrate, learn, and go on with their everyday lives.

Level of Social Support of Students in Special Program for Sports

Table 2 presents the results of the study on the level of social support of students in terms of companionship, emotional, informational, instrumental, and validation support. The overall mean for social support of students for sports among public schools in Region XI is 3.57 which is described as a high level. The high level implies that the social support of students is oftentimes evident. This implies

that the students gain significant social support from a network of peers, coaches, and staff who are genuinely committed to their performance, generating a sense of belonging, camaraderie, and personal value. The overall standard deviation is .49 less than 1.00 which represented uniformity of responses from the participants near the mean value and implies that the responses are not so dispersed from each other. The result supports the study of Sam (2013) stating that having people to turn to in times of need or crisis, including friends and family, may help you focus more broadly and project a more positive image of yourself. One's quality of life may rise in tandem with a buffer against the adverse effects of challenging circumstances provided by a solid social support network.

Table 2. Level of Social Support of Students in Special Program for Sports

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Companionship Support	3.55	0.75	High
Emotional Support	3.52	0.74	High
Informational Support	3.71	0.73	High
Instrumental Support	3.56	0.72	High
Validation Support	3.52	0.73	High
Overall Mean	3.57	0.49	High

The indicator with the highest mean is information support. The means of this indicator information support ranged from 3.61 to 3.79. The category mean is 3.71 described as high which means information support is oftentimes evident. This means that high levels of information support provide athletes with comprehensive knowledge about the technical aspects, strategies, and tactics relevant to their sport that leads them to gain a deeper understanding of their performance. The foregoing result is in congruence with the study of Fritz and Murphy (2018) which highlights the positive impacts of feedback interventions in encouraging physical activity, suggesting that they could be a successful tool for behavioral regulation. It shows that feedback enhances to encourage people to engage in more physical activity, guiding public health initiatives meant to improve population-wide activity levels and health outcomes. Also, this is in consonance with the study of Wu et al. (2019) which exposed that informational assistance provides individuals with advice, direction, or valuable information that enables them to solve problems or make sound decisions that leads to improve and value the activities. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest mean is emotional support. The means of this indicator emotional support ranged from 3.41 to 3.61. The category mean is 3.52 described as high which means emotional support is oftentimes evident. This means that students set expectations based on their performance and compare it to others. The finding is parallel with the study of Jones and Harwood (2018) that delved into athletes' motivations for seeking information about their competitors' performances. They found that athletes evaluate their personal development as well as to get confidence and a sense of belonging from the sports community. By evaluating their results against those of their peers, athletes can discover areas of strength and growth that will motivate them to perform well. Moreover, this desire for comparative information fosters a supportive environment within the sporting community, where athletes feel a sense of camaraderie and mutual encouragement.

Level of Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction of Students in Special Program for Sports

Table 3 presents the results of the study on the level of basic psychological needs satisfaction of students in terms of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The overall mean for basic psychological needs satisfaction of students for special program for sports among public schools in Region XI 3.72 which is described as a high level. This means that basic psychological needs satisfaction is oftentimes manifested. This means that basic psychological needs satisfaction of the students is often evident. This implies that students foster deliberate practices that lead them to have a strong drive-in goal setting and skill refinement that improves teamwork contributing to better outcomes. The overall standard deviation is .55 less than 1.00 which represented uniformity of responses from the participants near the mean value and implies that the responses are not so dispersed from each other. The results corroborate with the study of Ryan and Deci (2017), citing that the level of basic psychological needs satisfaction among students has indicated its crucial role in their overall well-being and academic success. Studies have shown that high levels of satisfaction of basic psychological needs, including autonomy, competence, and relatedness better academic performance, and improved psychological health among students.

Table 3. Level of Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction of Students in Special Program for Sports

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Autonomy	3.71	0.71	High
Competence	3.72	0.72	High
Relatedness	3.74	0.71	High
Overall Mean	3.72	0.55	High

The indicator with the highest mean is relatedness. The means of this indicator relatedness ranged from 3.66 to 3.85. The category mean is 3.74 described as high which means relatedness is oftentimes manifested. This means that building a sense of camaraderie among athletes not only improves performance and teamwork but also increases motivation, skill development, and mental health by creating supportive environments with teammates, trainers, and officials. The findings are similar with the study of Martino (2017) that we need relatedness to care for others, feel connected to them, and be cared for by them. Being surrounded by people does not satisfy

this need. We can satisfy it by being a part of a group or community and having genuine, close relationships with others. If people feel alone, excluded, or ostracized, it is likely that their need for relatedness is being met. Additionally, it patterns with the findings of the study of Ryan and Deci (2017) emphasizing the significance of relatedness to overall well-being. People have greater life satisfaction, happiness, and positive affect when they have satisfied social connections and a sense of belonging. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest mean is autonomy. The means of this indicator autonomy ranged from 3.64 to 3.78. The category mean is 3.71 described as high which means autonomy is oftentimes manifested. This means that giving students different activities that they like boosts their motivation, leading to more active participation and enjoyment as they take ownership of their training and goals. The results jive with the study of Hall (2017) stating when a person takes responsibility for their actions, controls them, and can make their own decisions. When they have the freedom to pursue their interests and values and believe that their actions reflect who they are, they satisfy this need. On the other hand, if they feel like they must do something because of pressure or force, their need for autonomy is frustrating. Additionally, this corroborates with the avowal of Weinstein et al. (2012) which cited that being independent or even rebellious is not the same thing as being autonomous. You satisfy this need regardless of whether someone has asked you to do something or not when what you do is the result of your choice.

Level of Behavioral Regulation in Exercise of Students in Special Program for Sports

Table 4 presents the results of the study on the level of behavioral regulation in exercise of students in terms amotivation, external, introjected, identified, integrated and intrinsic regulation. The overall mean for behavioral regulation in exercise is 3.48 which is described as a high. The overall standard deviation is .34 less than 1.00 which represented similarity of responses from the participants and the responses are not so dispersed from each other. The high-level means that behavioral regulation in exercise of the students is oftentimes demonstrated. This means that a high level of behavioral regulation in student exercise indicates the importance of targeted interventions and supportive environments to encourage consistent physical activity participation. The findings corroborate the study of Lee & Jin (2015) that explains the behavioral regulation in exercise among students is still emerging, but cultural, social, and educational factors likely influence their exercise habits and regulatory mechanisms. Society places a strong emphasis on academic achievement, potentially leading to a moderate level of engagement in physical activity as students prioritize studying.

Table 4. *Level of Behavioral Regulation in Exercise of Students in Special Program for Sports*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Amotivation	3.01	1.09	Moderate
External Regulation	3.23	0.95	Moderate
Introjected Regulation	3.53	0.85	High
Identified Regulation	3.67	0.78	High
Integrated Regulation	3.63	0.81	High
Intrinsic Regulation	3.79	0.86	High
Overall Mean	3.48	0.34	High

The indicator with the highest mean is intrinsic regulation. The means of this indicator intrinsic regulation ranged from 3.76 to 3.83. The category mean is 3.79 described as high which means intrinsic regulation is oftentimes demonstrated. This means students engage in their sport for the enjoyment, satisfaction, and personal fulfilment it provides. Athletes who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to demonstrate sustained effort, dedication, and commitment to their training and competition leading to consistent progress and performance improvement. The findings jive with the study of Winiger (2017), stating that those who are intrinsically motivated to exercise do so for the enjoyment they get out of it. Opposes behaviors with extrinsically motivated contingent outcomes distinct from behavior. In addition, it substantiates the avowal of Addict (2018) who asserted that human motivation relies on an individual's innate capacity to incorporate their experiences into an appropriate internal structure. Sustaining a strong motivation for exercise is indeed necessary to cultivate an unhealthy attachment. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest mean is amotivation. The means of this indicator amotivation ranged from 2.91 to 3.09. The category mean is 2.87 described as moderate which means amotivation is sometimes manifested. This implies that students who are suffering from moderate levels of amotivation may exhibit decreased effort, energy, and engagement in their sport. They might not be motivated, excited, or have a clear goal for their training and competition, which would result in less ideal performance and leads to slow advancement. This finding conforms with the study of Perera (2022) stating there are many barriers that participants reported to being active. These included competing priorities work, physical concerns, health concerns, resources as well as lack of understanding of the importance of physical activity for health. Also, it confirms the avowal of Physiopedia (2018) which mentioned that not enough time, no one to exercise, and lack of facilities were the most common external barriers among the respondents, which explains that identify the external and internal barriers to physical activity and exercise participation.

Significance of the influence of Sleep Quality, Social Support, Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction and Behavioral Regulation of Exercise of Special Program for Sports Students.

Reflected in Table 5 is the significance of the relationship of the four variables in the study. It can be deduced that there is a significant relationship between social support and behavior regulation in exercise as indicated by a p-value less than .05, which rejects the null

hypothesis. A correlation coefficient of 0.194 indicates a positive very low relationship. In addition, basic psychological needs satisfaction is also observed to have significant relationship with behavior regulation in exercise ($p < .05$). A correlation coefficient of 0.255 indicates a positive low relationship. The significant relationship between social support and behavioral regulation in exercise suggests that students who are in special program for sports and receive high levels of social support are more likely to exhibit increased behavioral regulation in exercise. The findings are congruent with the study of Wilson et al. (2019) found that social support significantly influences behavioral regulation of exercise of college students' as it influences their commitment and motivation to engage in physical activity. Additionally, it shows that students are more likely to adhere to regular physical activity when they feel social support from friends, family, and peers. It serves as a motivating element that strengthens people's drive to go beyond obstacles and difficulties, which improves their capacity to successfully control their exercise behavior. It also affirms the assumption of Egan & Bull (2020) mentioned that positive behavior is greatly impacted by a strong sense of social support from friends, family, and significant others, which may assist lower risk-taking and other activity.

Table 5. Significant Influence of Sleep Quality, Social Support, Basic Psychological Needs Satisfaction and Behavioral Regulation of Exercise of Special Program for Sports Students

Variables	R	p-value	Remarks
Sleep Quality and Behavior Regulation in Exercise of Students in Special Program for Sports	-0.091	0.083	Not Significant
Social Support and Behavior Regulation in Exercise of Students in Special Program for Sports	0.194	0.000	Significant
Basic psychological needs satisfaction and Behavior Regulation in Exercise of Students in Special Program for Sports	0.255	0.000	Significant

***Significant at 0.005

On the other hand, there is a significant relationship between basic psychological needs satisfaction and behavioral regulation in exercise of students in special program for sports. This indicates that the increase in the basic psychological need satisfaction of students would contribute to their higher behavior regulation in exercise. The results jive with the study of Davies et al. (2016), citing that a good provision of the basic psychological need satisfaction allow students to have better behavior regulation in exercise. Notably, students with low competence, autonomy, and relatedness have poor behavior regulation in exercise. On the other hand, San (2021) argued that meeting the fundamental psychological requirements was assumed to lead to positive outcomes to behavior regulation in exercise cannot be satisfied if they have not met their psychological needs. People can make decisions better, comprehend what is expected of them, feel at ease, and have the energy to tackle problems when their psychological needs are met.

However, sleep quality and behavior regulation in exercise are found to be not significantly related as indicated in the table having 0.083 p-value > 0.005 and a correlation coefficient of -0.091. This implies that sleep quality does not have a direct contribution to the behavioral regulation in exercise among special programs for sports students in region XI.

Test of Hypothesized Models

Figure 1 shows the test of hypothesized model that is not good fit. The figure reveals that a total of 15% of variance of behavior regulation in exercise is explained by the combined influence of sleep quality, social support, and basic psychological needs satisfaction. Sleep quality and basic psychological needs satisfaction do not significantly predict behavior regulation in exercise having beta values of .03 and .02, respectively. It is only social support that significantly influences behavior regulation in exercise, revealing a beta value of .38 ($p < .05$).

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model

Table 6 shows the goodness of fit indices for the hypothesized model: CMIN/DF = 52.505, Chi-Square p-value = 0.000, TLI = 1.012, CFI = 1.000, RMSEA = 0.679, and p-close = 0.000. The CMIN/DF, Chi-Square p-value, and p-close do not fit the indices criteria; therefore, this model is not a good-fit model for behavior regulation in exercise.

Table 6. *Goodness of Fit Indices of the Hypothesized Model*

Index	Criteria	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	< 3.0	52.505
Chi-Square p-value	> 0.05	0.000
TLI	> 0.90	1.012
CFI	> 0.90	1.000
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.679
p-close	> 0.05	0.000

Best Fit Model for Behavior Regulation in Exercise

Figure 2 shows the test of best fit hypothesized model. It can be gleaned in the model that 15% of the variance of behavioral regulation in exercise can be attributed to the combined influence of sleep quality, social support, and basic psychological needs satisfaction. Moreover, sleep quality and basic psychological needs satisfaction have no direct effect upon behavior regulation in exercise. However, sleep quality has direct effect to basic psychological needs satisfaction, showing a beta value of 0.46. Also, basic psychological needs satisfaction has direct effect on the social support, revealing a beta value of 0.62.

Figure 2. *Best Fit Model*

Table 7 displayed the direct, indirect, and total effects of exogenous variable to the endogenous variable. It can be observed in the results that social support is statistically significant direct effect on the behavioral regulation in exercise with p- value < 0.05 and showing a beta value of 0.39. To elaborate, sleep quality indirectly affects behavior regulation in exercise by influencing the basic psychological needs satisfaction. Moreover, the basic psychological needs satisfaction indirectly affects behavior regulation in exercise through its direct influence on social support with a beta value of 0.24 and p-value of 0.10.

Table 7. *Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of the Best-Fit Model*

Independent Variables	Direct Effect	p	Indirect Effect	p	Total Effect	P
Sleep Quality	-	-	-	-	-	-
Social Support	.387	.000	-	-	.387	.000
Basic Psychologic Needs Satisfaction	-	-	.239	.010	.239	.000

Table 8 shows the results of the goodness of fit measures of the hypothesized model. All model fit values have successfully met the criteria set by each index. It revealed the following indices: CMIN/DF = 0.309; Chi-Square p-value = 0.415, TLI = 1.013, CFI = 1.000, RMSEA = 0.054, and p-close = 0.941. Therefore, this model is the best fit model for behavior regulation in exercise.

Table 8. *Goodness of Fit Indices of the Best Fit Model*

Index	Criteria	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	< 3.0	0.309
Chi-Square p-value	> 0.05	0.415
TLI	> 0.90	1.013
CFI	> 0.90	1.000
RMSEA	< 0.08	0.054
p-close	> 0.05	0.941

On the aspect of sample size, this study has more than the minimum acceptable size of 200 for path analysis (Boomsma, 1982). The total sample of 370 indicates that the sample size used in this study is adequate to yield an appropriate model fit. The model is a product of a seemingly more elaborated theory where there is a removal of weak influencing variables that are observed as not significantly linked to the other variables in other models.

These findings align with the study of Egan and Bull (2020) which revealed that positive behavior is greatly impacted by a strong sense of social support from friends, family, and significant others, which may assist lower risk-taking and other activity. Also, it affirms the statement expressed in the article written in the Primary Healthcare Project (2017) stating having family and friends you can turn to in difficult times might help you focus more on the situation at hand and cultivate a positive self-image.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were deduced: The level of sleep quality of the students comprising the special program for sports students in Region XI is moderate, which signifies that the sleep quality of the students is sometimes manifested. This implies that students had problems with sleep, having decreased appetite due to poor sleep, and having difficulty in getting back to sleep, thereby interfering with their daily life. The level of social support of the students comprising the special program for sports students in Region XI is high, which signifies that the social support of the students is oftentimes evident. This further implies that students are getting positive feedback and reassurance as well as other support from family and friends. The level of basic psychological needs satisfaction of the students comprising the special program for sports students in Region XI is high, which signifies that the basic psychological needs satisfaction of the students is oftentimes manifested. This further implies that students have the control or autonomy over their choices and interests, making huge progress with respect to the results they pursue, and being able to manage the requirements of the training program they are involved with. The level of behavioral regulation in exercise of the students comprising the special program for sports students in Region XI is moderate which signifies that it is sometimes demonstrated. This further implies that feel under pressure from their family and friends to exercise, being guilty when they do not exercise, value the importance of exercise, and considering exercise as part of their identity. The significant relationships between social support and behavioral regulation in exercise as well as the relationship between basic psychological needs satisfaction and behavioral regulation in exercise imply that an increase in social support or basic psychological needs satisfaction would increase the behavioral regulation in exercise. Social support has a direct effect towards behavioral regulation in exercise. While basic psychological needs satisfaction and sleep quality have no direct effects towards behavioral regulation in exercise, there is still a need to improve sleep quality to have an indirect effect towards basic psychological needs satisfaction, which creates a rippling effect to improve social support.

The sleep quality is moderate and hence, there is a need to improve the sleep quality of the students. This can be improved through a seminar among students dealing with problems and discussing to them the importance of time management, the effects of screen time, and exercise. The social support among students is high. This can further be improved by conducting a seminar on parents and family members through the improvement of parent-child communication, reaching out to school authorities, talking to guidance counselors, and meeting other students sharing the same activities and interests. The basic psychological needs satisfaction is high. This can be improved by allowing and supporting students with their choices and interests, thereby gaining full control or autonomy on them with help of the school authorities like the teacher-coaches, sports coordinator, and school head. This can also be improved by allowing students to decide for themselves and respecting their choices as well as create an open channel of communication with other exercise participants. The behavioral regulation in exercise is moderate. This can further be improved through a seminar among students about motivation and allowing them to participate in exercises that are fun and pleasurable. Furthermore, teacher-coaches may redesign the activities that will allow students of different backgrounds to participate in exercises that are fun and engaging. Social support and basic psychological needs satisfaction must be improved to improve the behavioral regulation in exercise among students. This can be done through a seminar-workshop with the students. Since the best fitting model for the behavioral regulation in exercise was best anchored on social support, it is recommended that physical education teachers and parents to increase their support to the students, thereby improving their behavioral regulation in exercise. Furthermore, the findings of this study may be used as a guide for improving behavioral regulation in exercise and implement a more appropriate pedagogical model in the physical education subject. Similar study may be conducted using a mixed-methods approach involving qualitative data collection from the lens of the students. The researcher recommends other variables that may have influence on the behavioral regulation in exercise among students that are not found in the study and consider expanding the study by conducting it in a larger scope.

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